

Measuring method and process analysis of void formation conditions for resin matrix composites

Yizhuo Gu Min Li Zuoguang Zhang Zhijie Sun

Key Laboratory of Aerospace Materials and Performance (Ministry of Education),
School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University,
Beijing 100191, China, E-mail: benniegu@buaa.edu.cn

SUMMARY

This paper focused on void formation originated from hygroscopic water in resin matrix composites during fabrication, especially for hot pressing process. A simple method was established to measure the relationship between porosity and processing parameters, including temperature and pressure, and the void formation conditions of carbon fiber/epoxy resin and bismaleimide resin were studied.

Keywords : Resin matrix composites, Laminates, Composite manufacturing,
Void, Defect

INTRODUCTION

For fiber reinforced resin matrix composites, void is a common defect which can seriously deteriorate the properties of composite parts. Voids form and grow during composite fabrication, so the processing parameters must be carefully controlled to avoid this defect. In hot melt prepreg/autoclave process, hygroscopic water absorbed by prepreg is believed to be the main source of voids, especially for zero resin bleeding cases, because hygroscopic water and water vapour bubbles can not be effectively removed without sufficient resin flow. For this case, Springer and Kardos believed that resin pressure must be larger than a critical value to prevent the initiation and growth of water vapour bubble^[1]. Kardos et al established a simple expression to calculate the critical resin pressure for circular bubbles^[2]:

$$P_c = P_{water}(T)X_{RH} - \frac{3\gamma}{r} \quad (1)$$

where P_c is critical resin pressure, $P_{water}(T)$ is saturated water vapor pressure at temperature T , X_{RH} is relative humidity where prepreg equilibrates with moisture, r is the radius of void and γ is resin surface tension force.

Although some researches have demonstrated the validity of this expression for analyzing the factors of void formation and guiding the selection of cure cycle^[2-4], the

accuracy and applicability of critical resin pressure is dubitable^[5]. Firstly, Equation (1) is only involved with hygroscopic water in resin and ignores the influence of entrapped air in prepreg stacks, which is an important source of voids, especially for thick composite laminates^[5-7]. Secondly, $P_{water}(T)$ and γ are difficult for measuring during cure process because of the complicated cure reaction and fabrication environment, so $P_{water}(T)$ is usually taken as the value in the ideal atmospheric conditions and γ is considered to be constant without obvious cure reaction. Thirdly, some studies showed that fibers influenced the void growth to a certain extent^[4], but this factor did not be taken into account for Kardos void model. Finally, the critical condition in Equation (1) denotes a stable equilibrium state, and void growth is impossible to happen when resin pressure is larger than P_c . However, it does not mean that void defect will occur when resin pressure is smaller than P_c , because voids grow slowly in viscous resin and pressure circumstance and the volume and quantity of voids might not have enough time to increase markedly before resin gelation. Beside these reasons given above, the optimized applied pressure can not be directly obtained based on the critical resin pressure in Equation (1), since external applied pressure is borne by fiber stress and resin pressure before resin gel point^[8]. The relationship between applied pressure and resin pressure is determined by many factors, including the compressibility of fiber bed, resin rheological property, laminate thickness and temperature cycle^[8-11].

This paper focused on the void formation generated from hygroscopic water for resin matrix composite laminates prepared in hot pressing process. A simple method was established to measure the relationship between resin pressure (or applied pressure) and porosity with isothermal gel condition. The effects of humidity, temperature, resin variety and fiber on the critical pressure of void formation were investigated using this method. Furthermore, the measuring critical pressure and the calculated critical pressure from Equation (1) were compared and the difference was analyzed. It is found that the proposed method is useful to evaluate the processability of resin and the measuring void formation condition can provide significant information on setting processing parameters for eliminating void defect.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

In this study, a kind of epoxy resin called BA9916 and a kind of bismaleimide resin called QY8911 were used, which were supplied by Beijing Aeronautical Manufacturing Technology Research Institute (BAMTRI). The carbon fiber prepregs of these two resins produced by hot melt method were obtained from BAMTRI. The resin contents of prepregs were about 36 wt%.

Measuring method of void formation conditions

In order to quantitatively determine the void formation conditions, a testing apparatus was set up, which is shown in Figure 1. This equipment consisted of load cell, column metal die and temperature control unit. The space in a die chamber for placing sample was between a plunger and a base mold, which had smooth and flat surfaces ensuring the uniform pressure. The diameter of plunger and base mold was 25mm. The die

chamber contained heater element and the temperature control unit adjusted the temperature inside the die chamber with the accuracy of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The external pressure was applied by load bar using a mini hydraulic machine. During measurement, a sample with 25mm diameter was put into the die chamber and cured in certain temperature and pressure conditions. In this work, a group of samples were respectively heated to a same temperature T_{gel} and were held for certain time until resin gelled and then cured in a high temperature T_{cure} . T_{cure} was 180°C and 200°C for BA9916 and QY8911 resins, respectively. The samples was applied constant pressure during the whole process. Then, the porosity of sample was measured. By the procedure above, the curves of porosity as a function of applied pressure for samples under certain gel condition were obtained, so the critical pressure of void formation $P_{c-measured}$, i.e. the minimum pressure without voids can be deduced.

Figure 1. Schematic of the measuring equipment for void formation conditions

Preparation of samples

There were two kinds of samples used in this work, including resin sample and prepreg sample. For resin sample, resin disks with the weight of 1g and diameter of 25mm were fabricated using a mold. The resin disks were treated in vacuum oven for eliminating entrapped air bubbles. Afterwards, the disks were put in a cabinet, which could maintain constant temperature and humidity circumstance. Finally, the resin disks were kept in the cabinet at ambient temperature until the content of hygroscopic water reached the equilibrium state at given humidity condition. For prepreg sample, prepreg was cut into several pieces of disks with diameter of 25mm. Then, they were placed in the constant temperature and humidity cabinet in same conditions as that for resin sample. After saturated with hygroscopic water, the laminate stack was laid up unidirectionally with ten-layer prepreg, and was used for measurement of void formation conditions.

Measurement of void content

The porosity of cured resin sample was measured by means of liquid displacement method. The cross section of cured prepreg sample was ground and polished, and then

the cross section was microphotographed at 100× magnification using an Olympus BX51M optical microscope. The micrographs were analyzed using a digital image processing software to determine void volume content of the composite laminate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Void formation conditions for resin

As shown in Equation (1), resin gel temperature and equilibrium moisture of resin are two key parameters affecting void formation. Lower gel temperature and equilibrium relative humidity produce smaller internal pressure of bubbles and driving force of void growth, so the critical resin pressure is smaller and void defect is easier to eliminate. In order to quantify the effects of resin gel temperature and the equilibrium moisture, resin samples equilibrium at 50% and 90% relative humidity cured with different applied pressure using the proposed method in experimental section. The selected T_{gel} of epoxy resin BA9916 were 130°C and 140°C, and T_{gel} of bismaleimide resin were 130°C and 145°C. Resin gelation at T_{gel} was ensured by maintaining enough dwell time at T_{gel} according to resin rheological property. The measured porosities as a function of applied pressure are illustrated in Figure 2. Notice that resin sample did not contain fiber and resin flow did not happen during the curing process, so the applied pressure was entirely borne by resin and resin pressure was equal to the applied pressure.

Figure 2. Profiles of porosity of resin sample vs. resin pressure with different gel temperature and sample equilibrium relative humidity.

The experimental results given in Figure 2 show that the porosity decreases exponentially with the increase of resin pressure for both resins, indicating the existence of optimal pressure for void elimination, i.e. the critical pressure. The curve of porosity vs. epoxy resin pressure at 140°C is above that at 130°C as shown in Figure 2, demonstrating that voids are inclined to grow at higher resin gel temperature. The case is similar for bismaleimide resin. It is generally believed that voids hardly grow after resin has gelled, thus resin gel temperature determines the maximum internal pressure

of void. From this point of view for avoiding void defect, the temperature cycle during composite processing should be established to make resin gel at low temperature. Moreover, Figure 2(a) exhibits that high humidity environment (high hygroscopic amount) also increases the probability of void growth and results in high porosity at the same resin pressure. Therefore, the applied pressure should be adjusted to larger value for wet storage and manufacturing environment.

From Kardos void model, resin surface tension force can slow down void growth especially for small void. As shown in Equation (1), resin variety with different resin surface tension force might affect the critical pressure. Figure 3 compares the curve of porosity vs. epoxy resin pressure with that of bismaleimide resin under same gel temperature 130°C and same equilibrium circumstance 90% relative humidity. It is clearly shown that epoxy resin BA9916 has higher probability of void initiation and growth than bismaleimide resin QY8911. According to the measuring surface tension forces of both resins using Wilhelmy method, there is no evident difference between BA9916 and QY8911. On the other hand, the viscosity of BA9916 is smaller than that of QY8911, i.e. BA9916 has lower viscous resistance to void growing, and this might be an important reason for the distinction of void formation of the two resins.

Figure 3. Comparison of porosities as a function of resin pressure between epoxy and bismaleimide resins gelling at 130°C using samples equilibrium at 90% relative humidity.

For the purpose of further studying void formation and eliminating condition, theoretical critical resin pressure P_c was calculated based on Equation (1) without considering the effect of resin surface tension force, and experimental critical resin pressure $P_{c-measured}$ was extracted from the curves in Figure 2. $P_{c-measured}$ was defined as the minimum resin pressure without any void, i.e. porosity is just equal to zero. P_c and $P_{c-measured}$ are listed in Table 1. It can be clearly seen that P_c is slightly larger than $P_{c-measured}$ in most cases in Table 1. This distinction between theory and experiment is mainly attributed to the viscous effect. It is proven again that the growth of voids in viscous resin is not instantaneous and the effects of resin rheological and curing properties on the critical resin pressure are significant.

Table 1. Comparison between theoretical critical resin pressure P_c and measured critical resin pressure $P_{c-measured}$ for void formation.

Resin variety	Relative humidity/%	Gel temperature/ $^{\circ}$ C	$P_{c-measured}$ /MPa	P_c /MPa
BA9916	50	130	0.10	0.13
		140	0.20	0.18
	90	130	0.15	0.24
		140	0.24	0.32
QY8911	90	130	0.15	0.24
		145	0.29	0.37

Void formation conditions for prepreg stack

By means of the method used in previous section, the void formation conditions of carbon fiber prepreg samples were investigated, as exhibited in Figure 4. Applied pressure was partially carried by fiber bed, so resin pressure is small than applied pressure. Similarly to resin, the porosity of unidirectional laminate nearly decreases exponentially with the increase of applied pressure for both prepregs, while it need a greater applied pressure to remove voids for prepreg samples than resin samples. Since fiber stress during composite process has relationships with many factors, including the compressibility, initial resin content of prepreg stacks, number of layers and resin rheological property^[8-11], the development of resin pressure during processing is complex, and can be calculated by numerical method^[12]. This subsequent work will be carried out for analyzing the critical resin pressure in composite processing.

Figure 4. Profiles of porosity of prepreg sample vs. applied pressure with different gel temperature and 90% sample equilibrium relative humidity.

Figure 5 presents the curves of porosity vs. applied pressure for epoxy and bismaleimide preregs under gel temperature 130°C and equilibrium circumstance 90% relative humidity. It can be seen that BA9916 laminates have higher void content than QY8911 laminates, as is similar to the case for resin sample. From the micrographs of the cross sections of composites given in Figure 6, there are more and larger voids in BA9916 laminates than those in QY8911 laminates under the same applied pressure, suggesting that the bismaleimide resin has a better processability for avoiding void defect. This result agrees with the actual engineering cases of composite manufacturing in BAMTRI.

Figure 5. Comparison of porosities as a function of applied pressure between epoxy and bismaleimide prepreg stacks gelling at 130°C using samples equilibrium at 90% relative humidity.

Figure 6. Micrographs of the cross sections of carbon fiber composites curing with different applied pressure after equilibrium at 90% relative humidity, (a)-(c) indicate epoxy resin composites and (d)-(e) indicate bismaleimide resin composites.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed a simple method for measuring the relationship between resin pressure and void content at controlled gel temperature based on Kardos void formation mechanism from hygroscopic water. The porosities as a function of resin pressure were measured for epoxy resin and bismaleimide resin, and the porosities as a function of applied pressure were measured for the corresponding carbon fiber prepreg stacks. It is shown that porosity nearly decreases exponentially with the increase of applied pressure and a minimum applied pressure to avoid void defect can be obtained. Resin gel temperature and humidity environment of storing samples have significant influence on void formation, which agree well with Kardos void model. However, the critical resin pressure calculated from the model is larger than the measured critical resin pressure in most studied cases, indicating that voids are easier to control in actual conditions. The reason might be the effect of resin viscous resistance to void growth. Moreover, the results measured from resin and prepreg samples demonstrate that void defect is more serious in epoxy resin BA9916 than in bismaleimide resin QY8911 at the same process conditions, which is attributed to higher viscosity of QY8911 and more significant resin viscous effect. These results provide useful guides to optimize processing conditions for controlling void defect in composites with hot pressing process. In addition, the proposed method is suitable for studying void formation course and evaluating the processability of resin, which are helpful to improve composite manufacturing quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge National Natural Science Fund Program of China for its support (Grant No. 50803002).

References

1. J.L. Kardos, M.P. Dudukovic, E.L. McKague, et al, *Composite Materials: Quality Assurance and Processing*, 96 (1983).
2. R. Dave, J.L. Kardos, S.J. Choi, et al, *International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition*, 32, 325 (1987).
3. D. Frank-Susich, D.H. Laananen and D. Ruffner, *Comp. Manuf.*, 4(3), 139 (1993).
4. P. Olivier, J.P. Cottu and B. Ferret, *Composites*, 26 (7), 509 (1995).
5. F.C. Campbell, A.R. Mallow and C.E Browning, *J. Adv. Mater.*, 26 (4), 18 (1995).
6. F.Y.C. Boey and S.W. Lye, *Composites*, 23 (4), 261 (1992).
7. K.J. Ahn, J.C. Seferis, J.O. Price, et al, *SAMPE Journal*, 27(6), 19(1991).
8. R. Dave, J.L. Kardos and M.P. Dudukovic, *Polym. Comp.*, 8 (1), 29 (1987).
9. T. G. Gutowski, T. Morigaki and Z. Cai, *J. Comp. Mater.*, 21 (2), 172 (1987).
10. V.A.F. Costa and A.C.M, Sousa, *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 42(1), 15(2003).
11. D.D. Shin and H.T. Hahn, *Polym. Comp.*, 25(1), 49(2004).
12. Y.Z. Gu, M. Li, Z.G. Zhang, et al, *J. Comp. Mater.*, 40 (24), 2257 (2006).